

Social Media Influence On Representations Of Gender Equality Among Users In South-South, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined social media influence on representations of gender equality among users in South-South, Nigeria. The main objective was to determine how social media influences the perceptions of gender equality among users in South-South, Nigeria. The study was guided by the social constructionism theory. The study adopted a survey method. The population of the study comprised 18,619,019 residents of Rivers, Akwa Ibom and Delta States, while the sample was 385 residents of the three states. The multi stage cluster sampling technique was used in the study to identify respondents who were issued the questionnaire copies. Findings of the study showed that social media has a significant influence on perceptions of gender equality through the amplification of voices on gender representations; advocacy and activism; awareness creation and education; positive gender representation and role models. However, stereotypical representations and misinformation on social media platforms also influence perceptions of gender equality. The study concluded that despite the influence of social media, there are still representations of gender stereotypes, perceptions of masculinity and femininity roles, discrimination and gender inequalities faced by women and gender minorities in South-South, Nigeria. The study recommended that the government and non-government agencies should organise campaigns aimed to create awareness on the importance of gender representation and gender equality in Nigeria.

Keywords: Social media, influence, gender representations, gender equality, South-South, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Social media has revolutionized communication, providing a platform for individuals to share their experiences, opinions, and identities. Its impact is profound, influencing various aspects of society, including gender representation and equality. Social media, with its interactive nature, offers a more democratic space for gender expression (Ringrose, 2011). Social media's role in advancing gender equality is multifaceted. It provides a platform for marginalized voices, enabling women to challenge traditional gender roles and advocate for their rights (Carter, 2014).

Traditional media has long been criticized for perpetuating gender stereotypes and limiting diverse representations of gender (Gill, 2007). Studies have shown that women are often portrayed in stereotypical roles, such as caregivers or objects of beauty, while men are depicted as leaders and providers (Gill, 2007). This limited representation can influence societal expectations and reinforce gender norms. In contrast, social media offers a more participatory and democratized space for gender expression. Individuals can create and share content that reflects diverse gender identities and experiences, providing a counter-narrative to traditional media portrayals. For example, social media has facilitated the visibility of non-binary and transgender individuals, who are often underrepresented or misrepresented in mainstream media (Cavalcante, 2018).

While social media has the potential to challenge traditional gender norms, it can also perpetuate existing inequalities and biases (Duffy & Hund, 2015). Algorithms that prioritize popular content can amplify stereotypical representations of gender, as content that conforms to societal expectations often garners more likes, shares, and comments (Bivens & Haimson, 2016). Additionally, online harassment and misogyny can create hostile environments, particularly for women and gender minorities, limiting their participation and expression on social media platforms (Jane, 2014).

Despite these challenges, social media remains a powerful tool for promoting gender equality. It provides a platform for feminist activism, enabling individuals and groups to mobilize support, raise awareness, and advocate for policy changes. Social media campaigns such as #BringBackOurGirls that mobilised support for gender-related causes (Mendes, Ringrose, & Keller, 2019), #MeToo, which highlights the prevalence of sexual harassment and assault, and #HeForShe, which promotes male allyship in the fight for gender equality, demonstrate the potential of social media to drive social change (Mendes, Ringrose & Keller, 2019).

In the context of the Niger Delta, social media can play a crucial role in empowering women and challenging patriarchal structures. By amplifying the voices of women and showcasing their experiences and achievements, social media can help to redefine gender roles and promote a more inclusive and equitable society.

Statement of the Problem

The advent of social media has transformed the landscape of communication, offering unprecedented opportunities for self-expression and social engagement. However, its influence on gender representation and equality remains complex and multifaceted. In South-South, Nigeria, a region marked by entrenched patriarchal norms and significant socio-economic challenges, the potential of social media to either reinforce traditional gender stereotypes or promote gender equality is particularly critical. As social media becomes increasingly pervasive, it is crucial to understand whether it offers a platform for challenging these stereotypes and advancing gender equality or if it merely replicates existing biases.

This study therefore, seeks to address these gaps by investigating how social media influences gender representation and equality in South-South, Nigeria. By providing a nuanced understanding of the issues, the study aims to contribute to the broader discourse on gender equality and the role of digital media in promoting social change in the South-South.

The objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine how social media influences the perceptions of gender equality among users in South-South, Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the extent to which social media acts as a tool for empowerment, enabling women and gender minorities to challenge traditional gender norms

Theoretical Framework

Social Constructionism theory

Social constructionism is a theoretical framework that posits that knowledge and meaning are constructed through social interactions and cultural norms rather than being inherent in the world. This theory, as discussed by scholars such as Berger and Luckmann (1966), asserts that social realities, including concepts of gender, are created and maintained through communication and shared understandings. Social constructionism is a sociological theory that posits that knowledge, meaning, and understanding of the world are not objective truths but are instead constructed through social interactions and cultural norms. This theory suggests that the way we perceive and interpret the world is shaped by our social context, including language, culture, and societal expectations.

Social constructionism suggests that many aspects of our social reality, including knowledge, identities, and practices, are not innate but are constructed through social processes and interactions. This perspective asserts that our understanding of the world is shaped by the collective agreements and shared meanings created by people within a society. In the context of gender, social constructionism examines how cultural norms, social institutions, and interpersonal interactions contribute to the formation and perpetuation of gender roles and identities. Constructivism proposes that each individual mentally constructs the world of experience through cognitive processes while social constructionism has a social rather than an individual focus (Young & Colin, 2004)

There are several versions of social constructionism with different writers making different emphases. Two distinguishing marks of social constructionism include the rejection of assumptions about the nature of mind and theories of causality, and placing an emphasis on the complexity and interrelatedness of the many facets of individuals within their communities. Causality may exist within specific cultures but much work needs to be done before these connections can be described with any certainty (Owen, 1995, p.15). Social constructionism involves challenging most of our commonsense knowledge of ourselves and the world we live in. This means that it does not just offer a new analysis of topics such as ‘personality’ or ‘attitudes’ which can simply be slotted into our existing framework of understanding. The framework itself has to change, and with it our understanding of every aspect of social and psychological life (Burr, 1995, p. 12).

Social media, as a modern communication tool, significantly contributes to the discourse around gender roles in the South-South. It allows for the expression of diverse voices and perspectives, which can challenge established gender norms and promote more progressive views on gender equality. For example, social media campaigns and hashtags advocating for gender equality can raise awareness and encourage dialogue around issues such as women's rights, gender-based violence, and the representation of women in leadership roles. These online movements can disrupt traditional narratives and promote alternative views that advocate for greater gender equality. However, social media can also perpetuate negative stereotypes and discriminatory attitudes. Misogynistic content, gender-based hate speech, and the objectification of women are prevalent issues on these platforms. Such content can reinforce harmful stereotypes and contribute to a culture that marginalizes women, particularly those from minority ethnic groups or lower socioeconomic backgrounds in the society (Okon, 2017).

Social constructionism theory provides a framework for understanding the role of social media in shaping gender identities and norms in South-South, Nigeria. The impact of social media on gender representation and equality in the South-South, Nigeria can be analyzed through the lens of social constructionism by examining how these platforms influence societal attitudes and behaviours. In the South-South, where cultural, ethnic, and economic diversity is significant, social media plays a crucial role in shaping public perceptions of gender roles and identities (Nwagbara, 2020). Through social media, users from South-South, Nigeria engage in the construction of gender identities by sharing stories, images, and opinions that reflect their understanding of what it means to be a man or a woman. These platforms allow for the rapid dissemination of cultural norms and values, which can either challenge or reinforce traditional gender roles.

Conceptual Review

Social Media Influence

The social media is a collection of internet-based tools that provide channels of social interaction, content sharing and collaboration. Specific examples include Facebook, Instagram, Google+, and YouTube. Social media have evolved from being a handy means to keep in touch with friends and family, to being used in ways that have impact on the society. The impact of the social media shapes different aspects of the societal endeavours like culture, politics, education, art, etc. Social media tools like as, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, etc. have largely contributed to the success of the electioneering process all over the world. Social media helps in performing surveillance function and mobilizing the electorates into making informed decisions on parties and candidates on whom to support or cast their votes (Anderson, Toyin & Kenneth, 2017).

Today, people are getting much more familiar with social media. People have started to use social media as a new method to learn information about the things that they are most interested in, those that are very popular in society, and even to use it to relax and waste time. Because of the efficiency that social media has brought to us, the ways of people's communication have dramatically changed.

Social media influence refers to the capacity of social media platforms to shape opinions, behaviours, and social norms among users and broader society. This influence is a result of the widespread and pervasive nature of social media, which allows for the rapid dissemination of information and the creation of online communities. Social media platforms, such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and TikTok, have become critical spaces for public discourse, social interaction, and cultural exchange, significantly impacting various aspects of life, including politics, culture, and individual behaviours.

Social media plays a crucial role in the rapid dissemination of information. News, trends, and opinions can spread quickly across platforms, reaching large audiences in a short period (Boyd, 2014). This capacity makes social media a powerful tool for shaping public opinion. Individuals, organizations, and movements can use these platforms to promote specific messages, influence public discourse, and rally support for causes. However, the spread of misinformation or biased content can also mislead and polarize audiences (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017).

Social media platforms contribute significantly to the formation and reinforcement of cultural and social norms. Influencers, celebrities, and everyday users share content that reflects and sometimes challenges societal values, behaviours, and lifestyles. The visibility of diverse voices and perspectives on social media can promote inclusivity and broaden understanding of different cultures and identities (Papacharissi, 2010). However, these platforms can also perpetuate stereotypes and reinforce existing social inequalities, depending on the nature of the content being amplified. Social media enables the creation of virtual communities where people with shared interests, identities, or goals can connect and organize. This feature has been instrumental in the rise of social movements and grassroots activism. For example, movements like #BlackLivesMatter and #MeToo have utilized social media to raise awareness, mobilize supporters, and apply pressure on institutions (Tufekci, 2017).

Social media influences individual behaviours in various ways. It affects consumer behaviour through targeted advertising and influencer marketing, where influencers promote products and lifestyles to their followers. This can drive purchasing decisions and shape consumer preferences (Abidin, 2016). Additionally, social media can impact health behaviours, such as diet and exercise, by promoting certain body images or lifestyle choices. However, this influence can be both positive and negative, as it can lead to harmful behaviours like body dissatisfaction or disordered eating.

Gender Equality

Gender equality refers to the equal rights, responsibilities, and opportunities for individuals of all genders. It is a fundamental human right and a critical component for achieving social justice and sustainable development. Gender equality involves the elimination of discrimination and stereotypes based on gender and the promotion of fair treatment in all aspects of life, including economic participation, education, healthcare, political representation, and social practices.

The concepts of gender equality and gender equity are based on the assumption that the distribution of opportunities, resources, and responsibilities between women and men should not disfavor either group.

Gender equality concerns equal rights (absence of gendered discrimination) whereas gender equity concern needs-based approaches (Hammarström *et al.*, 2014).

Gender equality in the domain of economic participation addresses issues such as equal pay for equal work, access to employment, career advancement, and financial resources. Despite progress, significant gender disparities persist in the workforce, with women often earning less than men and being underrepresented in leadership positions (World Economic Forum, 2021). Promoting gender equality in economic participation not only empowers individuals but also contributes to economic growth and development.

Legal and institutional equality pertains to the laws and policies that ensure equal treatment and opportunities for all genders. This includes legislation against gender-based discrimination, equal pay laws, and policies that promote gender parity in leadership and decision-making roles. Legal frameworks are essential for protecting individuals from gender-based violence, ensuring access to education and healthcare, and promoting equitable work conditions (UN Women, 2020). The implementation and enforcement of such laws are critical for advancing gender equality.

In Western society the constant establishment of instruments for the defense and advancement of gender equality in the face of the corresponding indifference of social and political structures based on gender stereotypes has led to a clear improvement in women's integrity and autonomy with relation to men. Thus, for example, it might appear that the roles assigned to males as provider of the family's economic support and females as carers have been removed from Western society, indicating that classic gender roles are changing.

Gender inequalities affect various aspects of life in Africa, including education, healthcare, employment, political representation, and access to resources. African women are more likely to die from communicable diseases, such as HIV, tuberculosis, malaria, and nutritional deficiencies than men. Even though there has been an improvement in maternal healthcare continentwide in the last two decades, sub-Saharan Africa accounts for around 70% of global maternal deaths, a consequence of gender bias in the distribution of healthcare. Women and girls in Africa also bear most of the burden regarding unpaid care and domestic work; they face a higher risk of violence at home and in public spaces and are underrepresented in the labour market and politics, governance and decision-making throughout the continent.

In 2019 (pre-pandemic level), the average labour force participation rate in Africa stood at 56% for women compared to 73% for men—a gap of 17 percentage points. However, this is an improvement from a gap of 23 percentage points in 1990. At the regional level, the highest gap is in North Africa, where the female labour force participation rate was about 21.9% in 2019 compared to 69.5% for men. North Africa has lower gender inequality in education, but this academic achievement does not necessarily translate into progress for women in the labour market. As revealed by the World Bank 2021 Women, Business and the Law (WBL) report, women in the region face unfair laws that economically disempower them. Countries such as Egypt, Morocco and Tunisia prohibit women from working in certain industries. In African parliamentary bodies, women hold an average of 24% of seats, while their presence in top executive roles is a meagre 7%. Despite local governments being perceived as entry points for women in politics, only 21% of African council positions are held by women. Nevertheless, there are standout examples of progress. Rwanda, Namibia, South Africa, and Senegal rank among the top ten nations globally for female representation in their parliaments.

Even in education, where the continent has made the most significant progress in reducing gender inequality, girls in sub-Saharan Africa are still the most disadvantaged regarding access to schooling compared to other global regions. A multitude of factors, including widespread child marriage (though on a downward trend), teenage pregnancy, poverty and the social norm of valuing boys over girls, constrain females' access to education in sub-Saharan Africa. Furthermore, the exacerbating effects of climate change further compound these inequities. African women, constrained by their societal roles, economic status, and restricted resource accessibility, find themselves disproportionately vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. Gender disparities in education have been a significant issue, with girls and women often facing barriers to accessing quality education due to socio-cultural norms, economic constraints, and

safety concerns (UNESCO, 2015). Achieving gender equality in education involves ensuring equal access, retention, and completion rates for all genders, as well as promoting gender-sensitive curricula that challenge stereotypes.

Gender equality in health and well-being involves equitable access to healthcare services, reproductive rights, and the ability to make informed health decisions. Women and girls often face specific health challenges, including maternal health issues, gender-based violence, and limited access to reproductive healthcare (WHO, 2021). Addressing these issues requires comprehensive health policies that consider gender-specific needs and promote the well-being of all individuals. Gender equality in political and public participation ensures that all genders have equal opportunities to participate in decision-making processes at all levels. Women are often underrepresented in political leadership and governance, which limits the diversity of perspectives and policies that address gender-specific concerns (IPU, 2021). Increasing women's representation and participation in politics is crucial for achieving inclusive and equitable governance.

Despite global efforts, achieving gender equality remains a complex and ongoing challenge. Deep-seated cultural norms, economic inequalities, and legal barriers continue to hinder progress. However, there are also significant opportunities for advancing gender equality. International frameworks such as the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 5, emphasize gender equality as a global priority (UN, 2015). Additionally, the growing recognition of the economic and social benefits of gender equality provides a strong impetus for action.

Social norms and cultural practices play a significant role in shaping gender relations and expectations. Traditional gender roles and stereotypes can limit individuals' opportunities and perpetuate inequality. Challenging and changing these norms is essential for promoting gender equality. This involves raising awareness, promoting gender-sensitive education, and engaging communities in discussions about gender roles and stereotypes (Connell, 2009). Achieving gender equality is essential for building a fair and just society, promoting sustainable development, and ensuring that all individuals have the opportunity to reach their full potential. While challenges remain, continued efforts and international cooperation are crucial for advancing gender equality worldwide.

Empirical Review

Onyekwere (2020) conducted a study on 'Gender Representation in Nigerian Media: A Comparative Study of Traditional and Social Media'. The aim of the research was to explore how men and women are portrayed across these two types of media, identifying any shifts in gender roles and stereotypes, and understanding the influence of these portrayals on societal perceptions of gender. The study also seeks to uncover whether social media offers a more balanced representation of genders compared to traditional media. The researcher employed a mixed-method approach, combining content analysis of media portrayals with interviews of media professionals and social media influencers. For the content analysis, Onyekwere sampled Nigerian television programs, newspaper articles, and radio segments from 2019, alongside a collection of social media posts from platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter. A total of 1,000 media outputs were analyzed to compare how often and in what ways men and women were represented. Additionally, interviews with 50 media professionals provided qualitative insights into the reasons behind gender portrayals in both traditional and social media.

The study revealed significant differences between traditional and social media in terms of gender representation. In traditional media, men were overwhelmingly portrayed in dominant and authoritative roles, such as politicians, business leaders, and experts, while women were frequently represented in domestic or caregiving roles, often objectified in entertainment and advertising content. This reinforced stereotypical gender norms, with women seen as secondary to men in many narratives. Conversely, social media demonstrated more diverse and balanced representations of gender. Women were more likely to be seen in leadership roles, as entrepreneurs, and as voices of activism, particularly in gender-related discussions and movements like #MeToo and #BringBackOurGirls. Social media allowed for greater agency, as women could create their own content, challenge stereotypes, and engage in discourse that challenged traditional media portrayals. However, the study also found that women still faced

objectification on social media, particularly in the realm of visual content, such as influencer marketing and entertainment.

However, while the study offers valuable comparative insights, it leaves several areas unexplored, particularly in relation to regional differences and the broader implications for gender equality. The current study however seeks to address these gaps. Unlike Onyekwere's research, which focuses on comparing media types on a national level, the present study narrows its focus to the South-South region of Nigeria, aiming to explore how social media specifically influences gender representation and efforts toward achieving gender equality in this culturally and politically distinct region. This localized approach allows for a deeper understanding of how regional social and cultural dynamics interact with online gender portrayals, a dimension that is largely absent in Onyekwere's broader, media-type comparison.

Eze and Okon (2017) conducted a study on 'Social Media and Gender Representation: A Study in the South-South'. The study sought to explore how gender is represented on social media platforms in the South-South region. This region, known for its unique socio-political and economic landscape, provides a distinct context for examining the interplay between social media and gender dynamics. The primary objectives of the study were to analyze the portrayal of different genders on social media platforms popular in the South-South; assess the impact of these portrayals on the perceptions and attitudes of the region's residents, particularly towards gender roles and stereotypes; and examine the role of social media in either reinforcing or challenging traditional gender norms. The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative content analysis with qualitative interviews and surveys:

The content analysis involved systematically examining a sample of social media content, including posts, comments, and advertisements. The focus was on identifying patterns in the representation of genders, such as the frequency and context of male and female appearances, the roles they are depicted in, and any associated stereotypes. The study included surveys and in-depth interviews with social media users in the South-South. These methods aimed to capture users' perceptions of gender portrayals and how these influence their views on gender roles in society.

The content analysis revealed that traditional gender stereotypes are prevalent on social media in the South-South. Women are often portrayed in domestic roles or as objects of beauty, while men are depicted in authoritative or professional roles. Survey responses indicated that these portrayals have a significant impact on the audience's perceptions of gender roles. Many respondents acknowledged that social media influences their understanding of what is considered acceptable behaviour for men and women. Despite the prevalence of stereotypes, the study also identifies instances that social media content challenges traditional gender norms. This includes content promoting gender equality, highlighting successful women in non-traditional roles, and advocating for gender rights.

The study under review primarily focuses on the depiction of gender on social media and its impact on societal perceptions of gender roles within the South-South region. It examines how social media content perpetuates or challenges traditional gender stereotypes and the resulting influence on local audiences. While the current study appears to expand the scope beyond mere representation. It investigates not only the portrayal of genders but also the broader implications for gender equality within the region. The key differences and knowledge gap between the two studies will be examined in this study.

Okoro, Nwankwo and Bello (2022) conducted a study on 'Social Media Activism and Gender Norms in the South-South'. The study aimed to understand how digital platforms are used to advocate for gender equality and address issues related to gender discrimination. The objectives of the study were to identify the types of social media activism related to gender issues prevalent in the South-South; analyze the effectiveness of social media campaigns in influencing public attitudes towards gender norms; and assess the impact of these campaigns on policy and social change concerning gender equality.

The study employed a mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative research methods. The researchers analyzed social media content, including posts, hashtags, and videos, related to gender issues in the South-South. This involved categorizing the types of activism (e.g., awareness campaigns, protests, educational content) and identifying key themes. The study conducted surveys with social media users to gauge public opinion on gender norms and the perceived impact of social media

activism on their views. In-depth interviews were conducted with activists, policymakers, and members of the public to gain insights into the motivations behind these campaigns and their effectiveness.

At the end of the study, the researchers found that a wide range of social media activism in the South-South, including campaigns against gender-based violence, advocacy for women's rights, and movements challenging traditional gender roles. Popular hashtags like #EndGBV and #EqualRights were frequently used to mobilize support and raise awareness. The study also found that there is a significant shift in public attitudes towards gender norms, particularly among younger demographics. Many respondents reported that social media campaigns had made them more aware of gender inequalities and more supportive of gender equality. The study also found that there are successful cases where social media activism led to tangible changes, such as increased reporting of gender-based violence and the introduction of local policies promoting gender equality. Activists emphasized the role of social media in amplifying marginalized voices and holding authorities accountable. The study recommended that there should be sustained initiatives to increase digital literacy, ensuring broader access to social media and enabling more people to engage with activism. The study under review focuses on how social media activism influences public perceptions of gender norms and contributes to social change. However, the current study expands its focus to explore not only social media's role in shaping gender norms but also its impact on broader spectrum of gender representation and its implications for achieving gender equality.

Olowe and Adeoye (2018) conducted a study on 'Social Media and Gender Stereotyping: An Analysis of Nigerian Online Spaces'. The study aimed to explore the influence of social media on the reinforcement of gender stereotypes in Nigeria. The authors were particularly interested in how gender roles are represented and perpetuated across popular social media platforms, including Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter. The study's focus was on understanding whether social media acts as a tool for challenging traditional gender norms or if it strengthens existing stereotypes in Nigerian society. The researchers adopted a content analysis approach to examine user-generated content on the mentioned platforms.

One of the most significant findings from the study was the dual role social media plays in both reinforcing and challenging gender stereotypes. On one hand, social media provided a platform where users could express progressive views on gender equality, particularly in spaces where activism and discussions on women's rights were prevalent. For instance, feminist movements and gender equality campaigns gained visibility on social media, giving women a voice to challenge patriarchal structures. However, the study also found that stereotypical gender representations were still pervasive in social media content. Women were often objectified, especially in visual posts, with many images and memes perpetuating the notion of women as sexual objects or caregivers. Men, conversely, were frequently depicted as dominant, decision-makers, or financial providers, reflecting the traditional gender roles still prevalent in Nigerian society.

The study under review primarily focuses on how social media perpetuates gender stereotypes in Nigerian digital spaces. Their research highlights how online platforms reinforce traditional gender norms, objectify women, and depict men in dominant roles, thereby contributing to the persistence of stereotypical gender portrayals. While this study provides valuable insights into gender stereotyping, it leaves certain areas unexplored, particularly in terms of regional variations and the broader influence of social media on gender representation and equality in specific Nigerian contexts. The current study addresses these gaps by focusing on a specific geographic region – South-South, Nigeria. It goes beyond the analysis of gender stereotyping to explore the relationship between social media and gender equality. The current study aims to assess not only how gender is represented on social media but also how these representations influence perceptions of gender roles, power dynamics, and efforts toward achieving gender equality in the region.

METHODOLOGY

The quantitative survey method was used in the study. The study focused on three states in South-South region of Nigeria namely: Rivers, Akwa Ibom and Delta States. The population of Rivers State is 7,679,420; the population of Akwa Ibom State is 5,258,208; and the population of Delta State is

5,681,391. The total population for the study therefore is 18,619,019. The sample for the study determined using Raosoft online sample size calculator to be 385. The multi stage cluster sampling technique was used for the study. Data was elicited from respondents using the questionnaire. Reliability was established after a test-retest method using Pearson Product Correlation Coefficient to be 0.82. The data collected were analyzed using simple percentage.

Data Presentation

Table 1: Whether social media influences perceptions of gender equality through multiplication of voices on gender representations

	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a	True	287	76.5
b	False	76	20.2
c	Can't tell	12	3.2
	Total	375	100

Table 1 shows that majority of the respondents are of the view that social media influences perceptions of gender equality through multiplication of voices on gender representations represented by 76.5% of the respondents.

Table 2: Whether social media influences perceptions of gender equality through advocacy and activism

	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a	True	265	70.6
b	False	99	26.4
c	Can't tell	11	2.9
	Total	375	100

Table 2 shows that majority of the respondents are of the view that social media influences perceptions of gender equality through advocacy and activism represented by 70.6% of the respondents.

Table 3: Whether social media influences perceptions of gender equality through awareness and education

	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a	True	302	80.5
b	False	64	17
c	Can't tell	9	2.4
	Total	375	100

Table 3 shows that majority of the respondents are of the view that social media influences perceptions of gender equality through awareness and education represented by 80.5% of the respondents.

Table 4: Whether social media influences perceptions of gender equality through positive representations of gender and role models

	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a	True	309	82.4
b	False	57	15.2
c	Can't tell	9	2.4
	Total	375	100

Table 4 shows that majority of the respondents are of the view that social media influences perceptions of gender equality through positive gender representation and role models represented by 82.4% of the respondents.

Table 5: Whether stereotypes and misinformation on social media influences perceptions of gender equality

	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a	True	321	85.6
b	False	46	12.2
c	Can't tell	8	2.1
	Total	375	100

Table 5 shows that majority of the respondents are of the view that stereotypes and misinformation on social media influences perceptions of gender equality represented by 85.6% of the respondents.

Table 6: Extent to which social media provide a platform to challenge traditional gender norms

	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a	High	205	56.6
b	Moderate	128	34.1
c	Low	35	9.3
d	Can't tell	7	1.8
	Total	375	100

Table 6 shows that majority of the respondents are of the view that social media provide a platform to challenge traditional gender norms at a high extent represented by 56.6% of the respondents.

Table 7: Extent to which social media allow women and gender minorities to share their experiences

	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a	High	316	84.2
b	Moderate	36	9.6
c	Low	15	4
d	Can't tell	6	1.6
	Total	375	100

Table 7 shows that majority of the respondents are of the view that social media allow women and gender minorities to share their experiences at a high extent represented by 84.2% of the respondents.

Table 8: Extent to which social media provide a platform to raise awareness about gender-based issues

	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a	High	286	76.2
b	Moderate	45	12
c	Low	33	8.8
d	Can't tell	11	2.9
	Total	375	100

Table 8 shows that majority of the respondents are of the view that social media provide a platform to raise awareness about gender-based issues at a high extent represented by 76.2% of the respondents.

Table 9: Extent to which social media provide a platform to advocate for people's rights to promote gender equality

	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a	High	233	62.1
b	Moderate	76	20.2
c	Low	56	14.9
d	Can't tell	10	2.6
	Total	375	100

Table 9 shows that majority of the respondents are of the view that social media provide a platform to advocate for people’s rights to gender equality at a high extent represented by 62.1% of the respondents.

Table 10: Extent to which social media provide access to resources and support networks that may not be available otherwise for women and gender minorities

	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a	High	283	75.4
b	Moderate	54	14.4
c	Low	29	7.7
d	Can’t tell	9	2.4
	Total	375	100

Table 10 shows that majority of the respondents are of the view that social media provide access to resources and support networks that may not be available otherwise for women and gender minorities at a high extent represented by 75.4% of the respondents.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research question 1: How does social media influence the perceptions of gender equality among users in the South-South?

Social media has a significant influence on perceptions of gender equality through the multiplication of voices on gender representations; advocacy and activism; awareness creation and education; positive gender representation and role models. However, stereotypical representations and misinformation on social media platforms also influence perceptions of gender equality. These representations shape public opinion and attitudes towards gender equality and gender representation.

Social media plays a crucial role in shaping perceptions of gender equality by providing a platform for information dissemination, dialogue, education, and activism. Also, seeing successful individuals who defy traditional gender norms can inspire others and challenge societal expectations. Social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, X, etc are used for communication for the dissemination of ideas, opinions and information to others, and for participation in discussion groups. It is not surprising that social networking and social media services are tremendously popular nowadays and it has a great impact in spreading information and influencing opinions. This reflects the tenets of the social constructionism theory which states that social realities, including concepts of gender, are created and maintained through communication and shared understandings. Social constructionism suggests that many aspects of our social reality, including knowledge, identities, and practices, are not innate but are constructed through social processes and interactions. This perspective asserts that our understanding of the world is shaped by the collective agreements and shared meanings created by people within a society. Knowledge and people’s conception and belief of what reality is become embedded in the institutional fabric of society (Berger & Luckman, 1996).

The views and the information imparted on social media platforms could greatly influence a number of users. Social media as a modern communication tool significantly contributes to the discourse around gender roles in the South-South. It allows for the expression of diverse voices and perspectives, which can challenge established gender norms and promote more progressive views on gender equality. This is in line with the study by Eze and Okon (2017) which purports that social media influences their understanding of what is considered acceptable behaviour for men and women.

Social media platforms provide opportunities for women and groups to the exercise of their right to freedom of expression on the Internet. They can use these platforms to tell their stories, share their experiences, express their ideas and opinions, and even campaign or organize social movements to call for the improvement of their lives and social status. The more robust the public discussions to address the problem of gender inequality, the louder the voices that would reach the governments. Given this, it could be said that through social media discussions people could put pressure on governments to implement public policies that will take gender equality into account. This is in line with the study by Olowe and

Adeoye (2018) which purports that social media provided a platform where users could express progressive views on gender equality, particularly in spaces where activism and discussions on women's rights are prevalent.

But, while social media can promote positive change, it can also perpetuate stereotypes and misinformation. Biased content and echo chambers can reinforce existing inequalities and hinder progress. It is essential to critically evaluate the content and engage in constructive conversations to foster genuine understanding and change.

Research question 2: To what extent does the social media act as a tool for empowerment, enabling women and gender minorities to challenge traditional gender norms?

Social media act as a tool for empowerment, enabling women and gender minorities to challenge traditional gender norms at a high extent by providing a platform to challenge traditional gender norms; share experiences; raise awareness about gender-based issues; advocate for people's rights to gender equality; and access resources and support networks for women and gender minorities.

Social media has revolutionized how people interact online, providing a space for individuals to share their stories and connect with a global audience. It is a powerful tool for driving awareness, advocacy, and action towards gender equality. Campaigns and movements on platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram have played a significant role in highlighting issues, mobilizing support, and influencing policy and institutional change. This study therefore agrees with the study by Olowe and Adeoye (2018) which found that social media provides an avenue for marginalized voices, its open nature also allows for the reinforcement of patriarchal ideologies.

Facebook and other social networking sites have been a major area of research, particularly to understand what practices and behaviours, mobile phone users like LGBTQ+, adopt during their self-presentation online (Haimson, Brubaker, Dombrowski & Hayes, 2015). The platforms differ in their self-presentation affordances or controls, which might influence how one projects one's image online (DeVito, Walker & Birnholtz, 2018). According to Walker and DeVito (2020), online spaces are filling the void for LGBTQ+ identity discovery and growth, as well as social support networks. Blackwell, Hardy, Ammari, Veinot, Lampe and Schoenebeck (2016) assert that as a stigmatized minority group, online platforms provide LGBTQ+ people more opportunities to reveal their sexual or gender identities, mobilize political ideas, and create 'safe places'. In spite of this, the level of acceptability among the Nigerian audience is still low. The Nigerian audience are still bound by the traditional gender norms and have low tolerance for LGBTQ+ people.

On the other hand, women social media provides an avenue for the empowerment women who have experienced agony and unfair treatments caused by gender inequality. They have used the social media platforms to a large extent to voice their opinions and experiences to millions of social media users around the world. Which has catalyzed more public discussions on gender inequality-related issues. This is line with the study by Onyekwere (2020) social media was found to be a critical space for women to challenge these stereotypes and engage in activism for gender equality.

The Internet provides new space where users can exercise their rights to freedom of expression through playing roles as both the speakers to a wide audience and audience who could access to a wide range of different ideas and opinions from various speakers, encouraging more public discussions. Social networking and social media platforms facilitate people, especially those who have common interests in the same social and political issues, to engage in the inclusive public discussions, which, in turn, would become a strength to demand for changes (Pitaksantayothin, 2023). A lot of women and gender minorities have underprivileged social status, limited opportunities and experience discrimination and unfair treatment because of gender inequality in their societies. Social media networking provides a powerful channel for them to voice their views and thoughts, embark on campaigns and social movements, as well as to make powerful calls to the governments for social and political changes.

CONCLUSION

Despite the influence of social media, there are still representations of gender stereotypes, perceptions of masculinity and femininity roles, discrimination and gender inequalities faced by women and gender

minorities in South-South, Nigeria. Social media platforms are used to propagate harmful stereotypes, such as portraying women primarily as caregivers or undermining the capabilities of women. However, social media platforms provide fora to challenge gender stereotypes, advocate for rights of women and gender minorities, and create avenues for campaigns to raise public awareness for social change on issues of gender representation and equality. Social media is a powerful tool for driving awareness, advocacy, and action towards gender equality in Nigeria. It offers a space for women, gender minorities and people from different ethnic and social backgrounds to express their views, challenge patriarchal norms, and mobilize for social change.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Government and non-government agencies should organise campaigns aimed to create awareness on the importance of gender representation and gender equality in Nigeria.
2. Social media platforms should be used to promote specific educational support and training programmes that will educate young people on critical media skills and equip them to navigate, challenge and reject harmful gender stereotypes in online spaces.

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